

Coastal Bluff Erosion Concern from Del Mar to National City

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Introduction

Coastal bluff erosion is a real issue in San Diego County because cliffs, waves, roads, rail lines, houses, and public access points can all meet in a narrow strip of land. A bluff can look stable from far away, but it can still be steep, close to infrastructure, and exposed to coastal processes. That is the basic problem for this project.

My research question is: which parts of the San Diego coast between Del Mar and National City show the highest concern for bluff erosion because steep coastal slopes and nearby transportation infrastructure overlap? This question matters because those are the places where a physical hazard is closer to people or public infrastructure. The goal of the map is to show a screening-level concern pattern, so the result can point to areas that deserve a closer field check.

The study area follows the coast from the Del Mar/Torrey Pines area south toward Point Loma, San Diego Bay, and National City. The map uses a narrow coastal corridor instead of the whole county because bluff erosion is mainly a shoreline and near-shoreline problem. Some inland context is still visible so the coast can be read against roads, canyons, and terrain.

Data

The raster dataset was elevation from the USGS 3D Elevation Program image service [1]. I used the DEM to calculate slope in degrees and to make terrain context for the final map. The output DEM cell size for this run was about 11 meters, which is detailed enough for a county-scale coastal screening map while still being manageable in ArcGIS Pro.

The main vector shoreline dataset was the California Department of Fish and Wildlife (CDFW) shoreline types layer [2]. This layer was used as the coast or bluff-edge line for buffering, sectioning, and measuring distance from the shoreline. The transportation dataset was SANDAG Roads_All [3]. Roads and rail lines were used as the infrastructure layer because they show where human use is close to steep coastal terrain. The final layout also uses an Esri basemap for geographic context [4].

The data were accessed in June 2026 through online GIS services. No manual geocoding was needed because the input layers already had spatial locations. I projected the analysis outputs into NAD 1983 UTM Zone 11N, EPSG:26911. The datum is North American Datum 1983. This projection is a good choice for this project because the analysis uses distances, buffers, and slope-related measurements in a local San Diego study area. A

latitude/longitude coordinate system would be less useful for this because degrees are angular units, not local ground distances.

Methods

The workflow was kept close to the normal ArcGIS Pro steps used in class. First, I added the DEM, shoreline, roads, and basemap data. I projected the analysis data to NAD 1983 UTM Zone 11N and clipped or selected the layers to the San Diego coastal corridor. Then I built a coastal analysis zone around the shoreline. For this run, the coastal analysis width was 3000 meters.

For the raster part of the project, I used the DEM to calculate slope in degrees. I treated slopes below 15 degrees as lower concern, slopes from 15 to 30 degrees as moderate concern, and slopes above 30 degrees as higher concern. I also used terrain shading as background context so the cliffs, canyons, and steep areas could be read more easily.

For the vector part of the project, I divided the coastline into short sections about 250 meters long. I used a 500 meter scoring buffer around each shoreline section so each part of the coast could be compared to nearby terrain. I also buffered the roads and rail layer by 50 meters to find places where transportation infrastructure was close to the coast. The important vector operations were clipping, buffering, shoreline segmentation, proximity selection, and a spatial join.

After that, I combined the slope and infrastructure information into a concern ranking. A section received more concern when it had steep slopes and nearby roads or rail lines. I then displayed the result as a continuous green-yellow-red concern surface. Green shows lower concern, yellow shows moderate concern, and red shows higher concern. The color surface fades inland because bluff erosion concern should be strongest near the shoreline and cliff edge.

Results

The final analysis divided the coast into 1189 shoreline sections. The ranking table counted 290 sections as highest concern and 12 sections as high concern. Another 289 sections were moderate-high concern, 587 were developed lower-slope coast, 10 were lower concern, and 1 was moderate concern.

Concern class	Number of shoreline sections
Highest concern	290
High concern	12
Moderate-high concern	289
Developed lower-slope coast	587
Lower concern	10
Moderate concern	1

The highest ranked sections had maximum slopes up to about 69.5 degrees and also had nearby transportation infrastructure. On the map, the strongest red areas appear where the coastline is steep and developed or transportation access is close to the bluff zone. The greener areas are lower in concern because they are flatter, farther inland in the surface, or do not combine the same slope and infrastructure conditions.

The result does not mean that every red area will fail first. It means that those areas have a stronger overlap of the factors used in this map. That makes the map useful as a first-pass screening tool.

Discussion

The main spatial pattern is that bluff concern is concentrated in the narrow coastal strip where steep terrain and infrastructure are close together. That pattern makes sense for San Diego because the coast has natural cliffs in some places and developed land or transportation corridors close to the shoreline in others. The map is most useful for comparing relative concern along the same coast, not for predicting the exact date or location of a future collapse.

There are important limitations. The DEM can show slope, but it cannot show everything that controls erosion. Real bluff failure also depends on geology, wave attack, storms, groundwater, drainage, shoreline armoring, vegetation, and recent cliff changes. The shoreline line may also represent the coast generally and may not be the exact active bluff edge in every place. Roads and rail lines are a good infrastructure proxy, but they do not include every building, trail, stairway, or utility.

Scale is another limitation. An 11 meter DEM cell is useful for this class project, but small cracks, undercut sections, drainage pipes, and recent landslides can be smaller than the raster cell size or newer than the dataset. A real hazard study would need field checks, higher-resolution lidar where available, local geology, historical retreat rates, and storm or wave information.

Conclusion

This project used raster and vector GIS analysis to rank coastal bluff erosion concern from Del Mar to National City. The raster work used elevation to calculate slope and terrain context. The vector work used shoreline sections, buffers, and nearby roads or rail lines to connect steep coastal terrain with human infrastructure. The final map shows that the highest concern areas are the places where steep coastal slopes and nearby transportation infrastructure overlap.

The Earth science point is that coastal hazards include both the cliff face and what is located close to it. They also depend on how the terrain connects to the shoreline. This map gives a clear first look at where those factors overlap and where a more detailed field or engineering study would make the most sense.

References

- [1] U.S. Geological Survey. 3D Elevation Program elevation image service. Accessed June 2026. <https://elevation.nationalmap.gov/arcgis/rest/services/3DEPElevation/ImageServer>
- [2] California Department of Fish and Wildlife (CDFW). California shoreline types GIS layer. Accessed June 2026. https://services2.arcgis.com/Uq9r85Potqm3MfRV/arcgis/rest/services/biosds3115_fnu/FeatureServer/0
- [3] SANDAG. Roads_All GIS service. Accessed June 2026. https://services3.arcgis.com/cWUrHVMNuGKfEAOj/arcgis/rest/services/Roads_All/FeatureServer/0
- [4] Esri and contributors. ArcGIS basemap data used for geographic context. Accessed June 2026. <https://www.esri.com/en-us/arcgis/products/arcgis-living-atlas-of-the-world/overview>

Bluff Erosion Hazard Map Along San Diego Coastline

This map shows where coastal bluff erosion concern is higher from Del Mar to National City. Red areas show places where steep coastal slopes are close to roads or rail lines, yellow areas show moderate concern, and green areas show lower concern. The colors fade inland because bluff erosion is most important near the shoreline and cliff edge. The land-side hillshade makes cliffs, canyons, and steep terrain easier to see. In this run, 290 shoreline sections were ranked as highest concern. This map is a screening tool, not a prediction of exactly where a bluff will collapse. A real hazard study would also need field checks and more information about geology, waves, storms, drainage, and shoreline armoring.

Legend

- Coastline / bluff edge
- Continuous bluff erosion concern surface
- Value
- Higher concern
- Lower concern

Coordinate system: NAD 1983 UTM Zone 11N (EPSG:26911)
 Datum: North American Datum 1983
 Projection choice: UTM Zone 11N keeps distance and area measurements reasonable for the San Diego coast.

Metadata notes: elevation was downloaded from the USGS 3DEP image service and processed as a local DEM. Shoreline data are from CDFW shoreline types. Roads/rail are from SANDAG Roads_All.